

THE USAGE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING DISCOURSE COMPETENCE OF PUPILS (IN THE EXAMPLE OF B1 LEVELS)

Abdukholiqova Sayramkhon Yusubjamol kizi

Fergana State University

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Abstract: The article considers one of the most important issues of modern foreign languages teaching: the innovative methods of developing language learners' skills in a target language deeply and systematically. Today specialists of foreign languages, namely teachers are demanded to develop learners' language skills and competences according to the measures and tasks of the study programs using innovative methods.

Keywords: social network, messenger, B1 level, online platform, virtual environment, means of multimedia

INTRODUCTION

First of all, we selected the appropriate sources, such as books, audio, video materials for the learners. For this step, we took the principles of learning a foreign language at B1 level into consideration. Also, we used the educational program of the students of the educational establishment as a basic source for the teacher.

Secondly, we gave all the explanations of each lesson on writing, reading, listening and speaking during the exact lesson of each skill using different sources, such as e-presentations, videos, audios and so on. After that, we uploaded all the materials onto the virtual platform day by day as well as supplementary daily informative materials for the learners.

Developing speaking skills: Firstly, we uploaded the materials which were used at the lesson onto the platform after the lessons at the university. This way we paid the more attention to the quality of the materials that we provided and the functions of the messenger. We presented the vocabulary lists for each lesson of the speaking skills in the form of information graphics to the learners in the virtual environment. Besides that, it is important to mention one thing that the infographics were varied and colourful for the benefits of the learners because it was crucial to draw the learners' attention to the subject they were studying at the university simultaneously. For example, we posted idioms, phrasal verbs, collocations or word patterns separately. Then, we provided the learners with the audio files as voice messages in which the words of the vocabulary lists were pronounced by us in order to teach how to pronounce them correctly.

Developing writing skills: According to the programme of the study for the first-year students, the main topics for the writing skills were to write paragraphs, such as narrative, descriptive ones and methods of presenting sentences in point-by-point and block ones. The theoretical rules of writing paragraphs in the target language were explained at the lesson at university, and the students were provided with the video lessons which were made by us on the themes on the platform of Telegram. To make the theories of writing paragraphs more comprehensive for the learners, we uploaded the e-presentations which developing listening skills.

Developing listening skills: The functions of the messenger Telegram enabled us to provide the students with a number of sources on the listening skills as well. First of all, we had some introductory lessons on the platform on the question types and strategies of the listening skills on the platform in the forms of e-presentations and infographics which were developed using special programs on PCs. Secondly, the tasks with the audio materials were started to be uploaded onto the virtual platform by us day by day by 160 day consolidating the materials which were taught during the lessons at the university. They were made using the Power Point.

Developing reading skills: The students were introduced the most effective strategies of reading skills during the lesson, and the e-presentation was uploaded onto the channel on Telegram platform by us. We, at first, worked on the students' reading strategies to reach the goal successfully. After that, the reading passages on the topics which were shown in the study programme were uploaded with the tasks into the virtual environment gradually. The multi choice, fill-in-gap, and True/False/NG questions were presented on the platform.

In the past, learning and education simply meant face-to-face lectures, reading books or printed handouts, taking notes and completing assignments generally in the form of answering questions or writing essays. In short; education, learning and teaching were considered impossible without a teacher, books and chalkboards. Today, education and training have taken on a whole new meaning. Computers are an essential part of every classroom and teachers are using DVDs, CD-ROMs and videos to show pupils how things work and operate. Pupils can interact with the subject matters through the use of such web based tools and CD-ROMs. Moreover, each pupil can progress at his/her own pace.

Technology allows distance learning: Perhaps the greatest impact of technology in the field of learning is its ability to help several people learn

simultaneously from different locations. Learners are not required to gather at a predetermined time or place in order to learn and receive instructions and information. All one needs is a computer connected to a modem (or with a CD drive); these tools can literally deliver a 'classroom' in the homes and offices of people.

CONCLUSION

All in all, the learners were provided with different types of audio materials on different issues in order to help them get accustomed to the target language more comfortably. These audio materials were downloaded from the special websites about environment, music, film, science, sports, politics, education and so on. The home tasks were received online after the lessons at the university and controlled by us to assist them if they needed any help while using the functions of the messenger. Interactive methods are very important in the development of discourse competence of B1 level students. The use of DVDs, CDs, audio files in them is highly efficient.

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